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THE ROLE OF SOCIAL CAPITAL IN PROFESSIONAL SOCIALIZATION OF PERSONALITY

The article analyzes the influence of social capital on the process and result of professional socialization of the individual, argues that in the mechanism of professional socialization social capital largely determines the choice by the individual of identification objects and value-normative system that will regulate his or her behaviour. It is emphasized that social capital of the professional environment in which the individual finds himself can not only promote but also hinder the accumulation of socially acceptable cultural skills, knowledge and information. This is due to the social and moral orientation of the value system on which it is based.

Keywords: *social capital, individual social capital, group social capital, professional socialization, professional identification, diffuse identity.*

Problem setting. It is known that every person is born with certain social statuses, which are determined by his/her belonging to definite social groups. As a result of the increase in the number of these groups, the individual acquires new statuses, which is accompanied by the expansion of the range of social networks in which the individual is involved, i.e. he/she increases his/her social capital. The strategic European integration course of the state policy of Ukraine, which is determined by the Association Agreement between Ukraine and the EU, envisages the formation and increase of social capital in Ukraine. This is, of course, theoretically and practically justified, because world experience shows that countries that pay due attention to its formation and multiplication have a much higher level of realization of human potential and satisfaction of social needs.

Analysis of recent research and publications on the problems of social capital and its impact on the process of socialization, shows considerable attention to them by representatives of various scientific fields – sociologists, political scientists, philosophers, economists. The scientific and theoretical basis for the analysis of social capital was laid in the works of P. Bourdieu [1], G. Becker [2], J. Coleman [3], R. Putnam [4–5], J. Turner [6], W. Stone [7], F. Fukuyama [8], which have already become classics and made the relevant issues multidisciplinary.

Domestic science was also involved in this area of research. Social capital in its various aspects was analyzed by A. L. Bagniyuk [9], A. A. Bova [10], S. I. Bandur [11], L. B. Barannyk [12], H. K. Volchkova [13], A. M. Grynenko and V. V. Kyryliuk [14], O. Demkiv [15], A. Drozdova [16], M. D. Lesechko and O. G. Sidorchuk [17], O. G. Mukhailovskaya [18], N. M. Polyvyana and O. A. Hrishnova [19], I. I. Semkiv [20], Yu. V. Sereda [21], O. A. Turetskiy [22], T. V. Shapovalova [23] and others. Thus, M. Ye. Horozhankina [24] in particular, proposed to consider social capital as a structural element of intangible capital that combines human, intellectual, cultural, symbolic, institutional types of capital and ensures the formation of general humanitarian capital of society. The author emphasized the need to capitalize the social sphere through the formation and functioning of humanitarian capital, which is created in the process of social transformation of society through the consistent accumulation of some forms of intangible capital by others. O. O. Ubeyvolk [25] explored the essence, genesis and modern forms of social capital. Emphasizing that the latter is realized in social relations, and therefore is not the property of the subject that uses it, so there is a natural need to invest in its storage and replenishment. At the same time, according to the researcher, the development of social capital in Ukraine continues to be significantly influenced by the “Soviet heritage”, when acquaintances and interpersonal relationships continue to determine the relationship between social actors. The negative external manifestation of such relations is the rapid and significant spread of corruption, which produces an environment conducive to the formation and strengthening of *anti-social* capital. This idea was taken up by O.H. Mykhaylovs’ka, who noted that one of the reasons for the low level of social capital in Ukraine is the spread of “negative social capital, which is manifested in corruption and fraud. Most citizens are not able to resist the corruption of government or antisocial behaviour of citizens” [18, p. 365]. It is almost uncontrolled today, and the transformation of social capital into antisocial is an extremely important factor that led to the definition of the *purpose* of our study which is the analysis of the impact of social capital on the professional socialization of the individual.

Presentation of the main material. Professional socialization is the basis of social behaviour in the professional sphere, which involves mastering the social principles of the professional community, transforming them into structural elements of the personality of the specialist [26, p. 802–803]. These principles are implemented in behavioural acts both in the performance of their direct professional duties and in informal interactions. When a person becomes a member of the professional community, the labour collective, he/she enters there with a certain “baggage” and receives internal status in this group. What this status will be depends on the individual, his/her belonging to other social groups, as well as on the values of the group. Over time, intragroup status may rise or fall, and the individual will

enjoy more or less respect. The ability to accumulate resources through different social ties depends on this. But such capital cannot be called social in the full sense of the word. In our view, status capital is most important for this phenomenon, and the relationships on which it is based can be formal or informal.

Individual social capital is related to the specifics of the norms of the group, and not to the characteristics of the individual who is included in the relevant social ties. According to these rules, each member of the group (unlike those who are not members) can receive additional resources. Thus, individual social capital differs from group capital only in the subject who benefits, i.e. accumulates resources [27].

It should be noted that individual social capital gained through membership in a group can have different consequences for the group itself. Thus, by bringing to the professional group his/her own social ties with representatives of other socio-professional groups, the individual expands the boundaries of group social capital, thereby increasing the effectiveness of the team as a whole. On the other hand, he/she may use his/her group's social network in such a way that it harms it. If such cases are isolated, norm violators will be removed from the group network, but if not, a "parasitic community" will emerge within the group, which uses its social capital to its advantage and can harm the system as a whole. Thus, in the process of professional socialization of a person the following situations may arise:

- the goals and values of the team and the individual coincide and are socially positive. This is the best option, the process of socialization is usually almost painless, and the social capital of the group and the individual capital of the employee are organically combined;

- the goals and values of the team and the individual coincide and are socially negative. This is the worst option in terms of social consequences, but the process of professional socialization also does not cause special problems, because the combination of capital of the group and the team occurs;

- the goals and values of the team are negative (false, backward, etc.), and the goals and values of the individual are positive. This situation leads to two possible consequences: either he/she remains in his/her position and is repelled by the team and, as a result, there are difficulties in professional socialization of the employee and combining social capital of the group and his/her individual capital, or due to the negative effect of conformity the individual accepts them, but then personality disorder may begin, psychological problems may appear;

- the goals and values of the team are socially positive, and the goals and values of the individual are negatively oriented. In this case, he/she often unites with the "periphery" of the team, the members of which do not have a clearly defined value system, and, uniting people around him/her, tries to either reorient the team "according to him/herself", or, without changing the positions, "do not stand out", and solve his/her own tasks. In this case, undoubtedly, the process of

combining social capital of a group and the individual capital of the employee acquires a distorted form.

This is *the first important thesis* we wanted to draw attention to.

Second thesis. Social capital consists of three main forms of ties: “shackles”, “bridges” and “links”. “Ties – shackles” means family and non-professional friendly relationships, “ties – bridges” refer to the relationships with colleagues, “ties – links” describe the interaction between members of large social groups. In the process of professional socialization, social capital will play a role, which is formed through membership in various social groups, but the decisive role will be played by “ties – bridges” and “ties – links”. Thus, the analysis of social capital at the microlevel is impossible without meso- and macrolevel analysis.

Group social capital (mesolevel) “works” when social relations contribute to the goals not so much of the individual but of the group as a whole, the realization of their interests. This can be achieved if individual members of the group will identify themselves with the group, share its goals and values, and the norms of interaction between them will help to fulfill the respective roles.

The analysis of social capital at the macrolevel requires emphasis on the significant spread of groups with a subculture of anti-social orientation in our society, as well as the presence of formal institutions the actions of which would be aimed at supporting each member of society. This means that for public social capital it is extremely necessary to have norms and values no longer of a particular but of a universal nature [28–29].

It is possible to use all types of capital – physical (certain physical qualities of other members of the group), material (their money), cultural (recommendations that facilitate access to other networks of interaction), human (knowledge and skills), status (ability to influence other people) etc., but only through social relations it is possible to increase any kind of one’s own capital.

Third thesis. Social capital can be characterized by two vector components: accessibility and volume. The accessibility of social capital is determined by the ability of each member of the group, regardless of his/her status, to obtain the resources of individual members of the group or the resources of the group as a whole. The volume of social capital is determined by the variety of components and the volume of capital owned by group members. By themselves, these components do not give an idea of the role of social capital in the process of professional socialization. Thus, the accessibility of social capital in its small amount is unlikely to help a young professional to socialize quickly and successfully in the profession. At the same time, large in volume, but not available to the employee social capital will not allow him/her to use the resources of the social network. Thus, social capital cannot be considered in fragments, offering the research on its vector components separately [30, p. 623–624]. A systematic approach allows us to trace the mechanism

of influence of social capital on the process of professional socialization in the dynamics.

The first stage of professional socialization is the formation of professional intentions. Professional self-determination is usually influenced by the immediate social environment and reference groups (“ties – shackles”). Firstly, through social ties, the individual learns certain values, his/her professional motivation is formed. Secondly, the social circle largely determines the possibility of accumulating the amount of physical and, above all, human capital that is needed to master the profession [31]. Of course, inclusion in certain social circles is not yet a guarantee of increasing cultural, physical and human capital.

J. Coleman noted that the human and financial capital of parents may be irrelevant to their children if parents do not play an important role in the life of the child, if their capital is used exclusively at work or in other activities outside the home [3]. This means that all types of parental capital must be complemented by social capital embodied in the family relationships. However, this embodiment has a downside. There are a number of parenting strategies that negatively affect a child’s future career choices.

Strict sexual preference forms the type of family upbringing, when a child of the opposite sex than expected is born, there is either upbringing of the child in the type of the expected sex with a strict imposition of corresponding interests and professions, or a decline in interest in upbringing and ignoring the child’s obvious abilities at all. Both options significantly complicate the process of professional self-determination and, quite predictably, further professional self-identification. *The desire to continue in the child their own line of development* leads to the fact that the child is actively imposed a professional direction similar to the parents’, which is often contrary to the true natural abilities and inclinations of the child, and for that the child’s circle of communication is artificially limited and programmed. As a result, social capital “works”, but professional identification is usually formal, professional motivation is situational, and professional marginalism becomes very likely. *Compensatory parenting strategy* is reproduced when the parents believe that the child is simply obliged to achieve what the parents failed to achieve. Parental pressure distorts the child’s personality, depletes the child before professional socialization takes place, and social capital is used solely to impose appropriate professional motivation. *Implementation of the “parents of the prodigy” scenario* (the child is focused on very high achievements in education, sports or art in an environment of increased responsibility and fatigue) and a strategy that characterizes *the desire to maintain parental authority at all costs* (the development of the child is deliberately hampered for the child would not exceed the level of the parents, including in the professional sphere), are essentially diametrically opposed, but equally flawed, because the total control over social interactions of the child

restricts free choice of profession, the child's career aspirations are artificially stimulated or, conversely, inhibited.

It is also necessary to note *the influence of the reference group* on the process of professional self-determination. Thus, a group role, often enshrined in a nickname, can largely determine a person's future professional goals, as it significantly affects the formation of a productive "I-concept". In this case, the same group role in different social environments can be assessed as positive and negative, which creates the need to either continue this role in future professional activities, or, conversely, to avoid it, i.e. in some way motivates to professional activity [32, p. 357–360].

The next step. Thanks to the social capital of educational institutions, the process of professional socialization can be adjusted, especially in terms of its main mechanism – identification. The structure of the personality undergoes significant changes during this period. And these changes can happen for the better and for the worse. First of all, it concerns the motivational sphere, which includes value orientations, ideas about professional role, motives, goals, guidelines that determine the orientation of the individual. And if the student does not receive support from those groups whose culture focuses on socially acceptable values, then the objects of his/her identification will be the individuals or social formations with other orientations, which in the future may lead to contradictions between societal demands for the corresponding social role and its performance by a person, which, in turn, will contribute to the emergence of professional marginalism. Thus, we again note the influence of social capital on the process of professional socialization, the functional significance of which acquires a special colouring. E. Erickson noted that adolescence is directly related to the identity crisis, which consists of a series of social and individual choices, identifications and self-determination [33]. If a young man fails to solve these problems, he develops an inadequate identity, the development of which has several variants: 1) self-isolation, avoidance of close interpersonal relationships; 2) blurred sense of time, inability to make life plans, fear of growing up and changes; 3) blurring of productive, creative abilities, inability to mobilize the internal resources and focus on any major activity; 4) the formation of "negative identity", the rejection of self-determination and the choice of negative images to follow.

J. Marcia et al., highlighting the stages of identity development, introduced into scientific circulation the concept of *diffuse identity*, which is characterized by the destruction of the internal integrity of the individual, forming a negative emotional background, dominated by passivity, pessimism, apathy and anxiety [34]. He noted that such an identity can be formed at the stage of premature identification, when the individual joined the relevant system of relationships, but did not do it by him/herself, i.e. as a result of crisis and trial, but on the basis of other people's opinions, example or authority, thus, based on social capital.

Professional socialization ends with a phase of professional activity. Its success depends on the quality of solving previous problems of professional genesis and the possibility of developing special professionally important qualities and abilities in the individual. This period involves a symbiotic combination of all three (micro-, meso-, macro-) levels of social capital.

Conclusions. The analysis of the role of social capital in the professional socialization of the individual allowed us to draw the following conclusions:

1. Social capital is inextricably connected with social relations networks. It cannot exist outside these networks, i.e. the availability of social capital in the individual is possible only due to his/her belonging to certain social groups.

2. Uncontrolled transformation of social capital into antisocial significantly affects on the professional socialization of the individual.

3. Social capital should be considered at the micro-, meso- and macrolevels. At the microlevel it is about the social capital of the individual, i.e. individual social capital. Mesolevel is the level of social groups. The macrolevel means society as a whole. The main criterion for distinguishing these three levels is the subject that uses the relevant social ties.

4. By bringing into the professional team their own social ties with representatives of other socio-professional groups, the individual expands the boundaries of group social capital.

5. Despite the fact that social capital is characterized by two vector components – accessibility and volume, these components in themselves do not give an idea of the role of social capital in the process of professional socialization.

6. In the process of professional socialization from the basic forms of which social capital consists of (“ties – shackles”, “ties – bridges” and “ties – links”), the ties “ties – bridges” and “ties – links” will play a crucial role.

7. In the process of professional socialization, social capital influences the individual’s choice of identification objects and value-normative system that will regulate his/her behaviour.

8. The social capital of the professional environment in which an individual finds him/herself can not only promote but also hinder the accumulation of socially acceptable cultural skills, knowledge and information. This is due to the social and moral orientation of the value system on which it is based.

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РОЛЬ СОЦІАЛЬНОГО КАПІТАЛУ У ПРОФЕСІЙНІЙ СОЦІАЛІЗАЦІЇ ОСОБИСТОСТІ

Постановка проблеми. Стратегічний євроінтеграційний курс державної політики України, що визначений Угодою про асоціацію між Україною та ЄС, передбачає формування та примноження в Україні соціального капіталу. Це є теоретично і практично виправданим, бо світовий досвід свідчить, що країни, які приділяють належну увагу цьому процесу, мають значно вищий рівень реалізації людського потенціалу та задоволення суспільних потреб.

Аналіз останніх досліджень і публікацій. Науково-теоретичну базу аналізу соціального капіталу було закладено в роботах П. Бурд'є, Г. Беккера, Дж. Коулмена, Р. Патнема, Дж. Тьорнера, В. Стоуна, Ф. Фукуями, які давно вже стали класичними і зробили відповідну проблематику мультидисциплінарною. Вітчизняна наука також не залишилася осторонь цього напрямку досліджень. Соціальний капітал у різних його аспектах аналізували А. Л. Багнюк, А. А. Бова, С. І. Бандур, М. Ю. Бондаренко, А. М. Гриненко та В. В. Кирилюк, О. Демків, М. С. Дороніна та А. І. Нечепуренко, А. Дроздова, М. Д. Лесечко та О. Г. Сидорчук, О. Г. Михайловська, Н. М. Полив'яна та О. А. Грішнова, І. І. Семків, Ю. В. Середа, О. А. Турецький, Т. В. Шаповалова та ін.

Формулювання цілей. Метою статті є аналіз впливу соціального капіталу на професійну соціалізацію особистості.

Виклад основного матеріалу. Професійна соціалізація становить основу соціальної поведінки людини у професійній сфері, що передбачає засвоєння соціальних принципів функціонування професійного співтовариства, перетворення їх на структурні елементи особистості фахівця. Ці принципи реалізуються в поведінкових актах як під час виконання своїх безпосередніх професійних обов'язків, так і в неформальних взаємодіях. Індивідуальний соціальний капітал пов'язано зі специфікою норм групи, а не з особливостями особистості, включеної до відповідних соціальних зв'язків. Отриманий завдяки членству у групі, він може мати різні наслідки для самої групи. З одного боку, привносячи у професійний колектив власні соціальні зв'язки з представниками інших соціально-професійних груп, індивід розширює межі групового соціального капіталу, тим самим підвищуючи ефективність діяльності колективу в цілому. З іншого – він може використовувати соціальну мережу своєї групи в такій спосіб, що це завдає їй шкоди. Соціальний капітал складається з трьох основних форм зв'язків: «зв'язків-кайданів», «зв'язків-мостів» і «зв'язків-ланок». «Зв'язки-кайдани» характеризують родинні та позапрофесійні дружні стосунки, «зв'язки-мости» стосуються відносин з колегами, «зв'язки-ланки» описують взаємодію між членами великих соціальних груп. У процесі професійної соціалізації певну роль буде відігравати соціальний капітал, який формується завдяки членству в різних соціальних групах, проте вирішальними будуть «зв'язки-мости» і «зв'язки-ланки». Груповий соціальний капітал (мезорівень) «працює» тоді, коли соціальні відносини сприяють досягненню цілей не стільки окремого індивіда, скільки групи в цілому, реалізації нею своїх інтересів. Це може бути досягнуто, якщо окремі члени групи будуть ідентифікувати себе з цією групою, поділяти її цілі та цінності, а норми взаємодії між ними сприятимуть виконанню відповідних ролей. Аналіз соціального капіталу на макрорівні потребує акцентуації уваги на значному поширенні в нашому суспільстві груп із субкультурою асоціальної спрямованості, а також наявності формальних інституцій, дії яких було б спрямовано на підтримку кожного члена суспільства. Це означає, що для суспільного соціального капіталу вкрай необхідним є існування норм та цінностей не партикулярного, а універсального характеру. Соціальний капітал характеризується двома векторними складовими: доступністю та обсягом. Доступність визначається спроможністю кожного члена групи, незалежно від його статусу, отримати ресурси окремих членів групи або ресурси групи в цілому, а обсяг – різноманітністю складових та обсягом тих капіталів, якими володіють члени групи. Самі по собі ці складові не надають уявлення про роль соціального капіталу у процесі професійної соціалізації, бо доступність соціального капіталу за умов його незначного обсягу не допоможе молодому фахівцеві швидко та успішно соціалізуватися у професії, а великий за обсягом, але недоступний працівникові соціальний капітал не дозволить йому скористатися ресурсами соціальної мережі. Системний підхід дозволяє відстежити механізм впливу соціального капіталу на процес професійної соціалізації в динаміці.

Висновки. Соціальний капітал нерозривно пов'язано з мережами соціальних відносин. Він не може існувати поза цими мережами, тобто наявність соціального капіталу в окремої людини можлива тільки завдяки її приналежності до певних соціальних груп. Неконтрольована трансформація соціального капіталу в асоціальний суттєво впливає на професійну соціалізацію особистості. Розглядати соціальний капітал доцільно на мікро-, мезо- та макрорівнях. На мікрорівні йдеться про соціальний капітал індивіда, мезорівень – рівень соціальних груп, під макрорівнем розуміється суспільство в цілому. Головним критерієм виділення цих трьох рівнів є суб'єкт, який використовує відповідні соціальні зв'язки. У процесі професійної соціалізації соціальний капітал впливає на вибір індивідом ідентифікаційних об'єктів та ціннісно-нормативної системи, що регулюватиме його поведінку. Соціальний капітал професійного середовища, до якого потрапляє індивід, може не тільки сприяти, але й перешкоджати накопиченню соціально схвалюваних культурних навичок, знань та інформації. Це зумовлюється соціальною та моральною спрямованістю системи цінностей, на яких він базується.

Ключові слова: соціальний капітал, індивідуальний соціальний капітал, груповий соціальний капітал, професійна соціалізація, професійна ідентифікація, дифузна ідентичність

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РОЛЬ СОЦИАЛЬНОГО КАПИТАЛА В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ СОЦИАЛИЗАЦИИ ЛИЧНОСТИ

В статье анализируется влияние социального капитала на процесс и результат профессиональной социализации личности, доказывається, что в механизме профессиональной социализации социальный капитал в значительной степени детерминирует выбор индивидом идентификационных объектов и ценностно-нормативной системы, регулирующей его поведение. Подчеркивается, что социальный капитал профессиональной среды, в которую попадает индивид, может не только способствовать, но и препятствовать накоплению социально одобряемых культурных навыков, знаний и информации. Это обуславливается социальной и нравственной направленностью системы ценностей, на которых она базируется.

Ключевые слова: социальный капитал, индивидуальный социальный капитал, групповой социальный капитал, профессиональная социализация, профессиональная идентификация, диффузная идентичность.

